

Adapting to Shifting Consumer Spending Habits: Key Trends for Retailers and Marketers in 2024

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Abstract

Summary

In 2024, understanding consumer spending trends is critical for retailers and marketers aiming for success in a competitive landscape. Key shifts include a strong preference for digital-first shopping, an emphasis on value-driven purchases due to economic concerns, heightened demand for sustainable products, and a growing inclination toward subscription-based services. Businesses that respond proactively to these trends can benefit from targeted strategies such as personalized marketing, immersive online experiences, and loyalty programs, all of which enhance customer engagement and brand loyalty. By aligning with evolving consumer priorities, companies can secure a lasting competitive edge in a dynamic market.

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